

Clinical variables investigation for the COVID-19 prognosis

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Introduction

Hospitals produce large amounts of data every day by exams and medical records and important insights can be extracted for decision making, including diagnosis and prognosis [1]. Studies about COVID-19 predictions has been related, such as the COVID-19 prognosis of patient's clinical aggravation [2]. If the disease's severity knowledge is anticipated, the most appropriate management of the hospital resources can be applied. Nonetheless, missing values and noises on predictive attributes in the medical records unfortunately is common, therefore data preprocessing is necessary [3]. The aims of this research is COVID-19 positive patients data preprocessing and Machine Learning (ML) techniques application in data from 4320 patients in order to detect clinical aggravation correlated variables and COVID-19 prognosis.

Methods

The data set used is relative to Hospital Sírio Libanês (HSL), available in the COVID-19 Data Sharing of FAPESP repository (<https://repositoriodatasharingfapesp.uspdigital.usp.br/>). The initial data set had 8971 patients and 954 kind of clinical exams. This data was applied to filters steeps, between them: repeated values removal; removal of COVID-19 positive proofless patients; first three days exams selection; emergency room exams selection; and removal of exams with more than 50 percent missing values. The preprocessed data were divided into four groups: Group 0 - patients with exams only from the emergency room (non-severe); Group 1 – patients with exams from emergency room and infirmary (non-severe); Group 2 – patients with exams from emergency room and intensive care unit (ICU) (severe); and Group 3 – patients with exams from emergency room, infirmary and ICU (severe). Five sets (S1 to S5) was created by different combinations between the groups (Fig.1 and Table 1).

Figure 1: Sets from groups combination.

Table 1: Sets description

Set	Target attribute			
	Non-severe	n	Severe	n
S1	Group 0	3393	Group 2	85
S2	Group 0	3393	Group 3	309
S3	Group 1	533	Group 2	85
S4	Group 1	533	Group 3	309
S5	Group 0 + Group 1	3926	Group 2 + Group 3	394

Each set was divided into 70% for training and 30% for testing. Only the training part was submitted to next steps: normalization, outliers elimination, missing values substitution to median of the class and under sampling balancing. The mutual information technique was applied in order to detect clinical aggravation correlated variables. Six ML techniques were applied in each set and area under the curve (AUC) were used

to measure the results. The ML techniques are: k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Decision Tree (tree), Decision Tree big variation (bigtree), Support Vector Machine with linear kernel (svmlinear), support vector machine with radial basis function kernel (svmrbf) and Random Forest.

Results

Preprocessing resulted in 4,320 patients and 27 exams data. The quantity of patients per group is Group 0: 3393; Group 1: 533; Group 2: 85; and Group 3: 309. The quantity of patients per sets is S1:3428; S2:3702; S3:618; S4:842; S5:4320. Considering only Set 5, the set with the most number of people, the 10 predictive attributes most correlated with clinical aggravation and its respective number of missing values are: 1. Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT/TGP) (1135); 2. C-Reactive Protein (1048); 3. Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST-TGO) (1152); 4. Age (0); 5. Creatinine (627); 6. Urea (778); 7. RDW (330); 8. Potassium (1011); 9. Erythrocytes (272); 10. Neutrophils (308). The ML results can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Results from six machine learning techniques applied to five sets data.

	S1 (n = 3478)	S2 (n = 3702)	S3 (n = 618)	S4 (n = 842)	S5 (n = 4320)
Algorithms	AUC (Mean ± SD)				
kNN	0.80 ± 0.09	0.86 ± 0.04	0.72 ± 0.13	0.67 ± 0.05	0.84 ± 0.04
tree	0.75 ± 0.10	0.86 ± 0.04	0.58 ± 0.07	0.77 ± 0.05	0.85 ± 0.05
bigtree	0.72 ± 0.12	0.76 ± 0.06	0.58 ± 0.09	0.71 ± 0.06	0.79 ± 0.05
svmlinear	0.85 ± 0.10	0.87 ± 0.04	0.73 ± 0.10	0.69 ± 0.07	0.84 ± 0.04
svmrbf	0.82 ± 0.13	0.86 ± 0.05	0.66 ± 0.08	0.64 ± 0.10	0.85 ± 0.05
Random Forest	0.92 ± 0.09	0.94 ± 0.02	0.76 ± 0.10	0.82 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.03

Discussion

The algorithm with the best performance for all sets was Random Forest. Through Table 2, it is possible to observe that the greater the amount of data for the set, the better was the result of the AUC metric, for example, set S2 and S5 have the highest numbers of data and the best results. On the other hand, set S3 has fewer data and a lower result. The mutual information technique results in the 10 predictive attributes, but some care is necessary about missing values in variables such as ALT, TGP and C-reactive protein. Because these variables have a high number of missing values, which can cause some bias.

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